

Review Protocol: Scoping Review of Acting in Social Virtual Reality for Immersive Learning

Abstract: This document is the review protocol for the paper titled Scoping Review of Acting in Social Virtual Reality for Immersive Learning. The main target of this scoping review is defining the research gap for acting in social VR for immersive learning. The research question is as follows: “What is the current state of research of immersive learning applications in social VR which include acting or role-playing as a major element?”

Keywords: Review Protocol, Scoping Review, Social Virtual Reality, Immersive Learning, Role-Playing, Acting

1 Information Sources and Search Strategy

The review has been conducted according to the PRISMA extension for scoping reviews [Tr18]. Three of the databases (ACM, Scopus and Wiley) used were chosen from the databases assessed as principal in [GH20]. Taylor & Francis Online (Tandfonline) database was also added to the existing databases, because it covers articles related to theater and performance studies. Date of search was 20.02.2026. The search has been conducted to focus on peer-reviewed papers for sustaining scientific validation and reproducibility. The search strategy is a modified Population, Phenomena of Interest, Context (PICO) framework [Mu18]. Since ACM and Scopus have generated too many irrelevant results, an additional key word, “virtual reality”, was added to the search query. Relative search terms and the resulting search query can be found in Table 1.

Format (PICO)	Terms
Population	multiuser OR multi-user OR "multi user" OR multiplayer OR mehrspieler OR multi-player OR cooper* OR collab* OR kooper* OR kollab* OR social OR sozial*
Phenomena of Interest 1	learn* OR lern* OR educat* OR bild*
Phenomena of Interest 2	role-playing OR "role playing" OR acting OR theater OR theatre OR schauspiel* OR handeln
Context	"virtual reality" OR "virtuelle realität" OR virtual-reality OR immersive OR XR

Tab. 1: The search string used

2 Inclusion Criteria

The inclusion criteria are as follows.

1. Head Mounted Display (HMD)-Based VR is in the focus, because this technology provides the user with the ability to act or embody a social role physically in a virtual environment. Extended Reality (XR) applications which include VR will be taken into consideration. This excludes desktop VR, augmented reality (AR) and mixed reality (MR) applications.
2. Multi-user social interaction in social VR learning applications will be reviewed. Applications that do not include social interaction between users are excluded. On the other hand, papers dealing with virtual agents are included. Human-robot interaction is out of context.
3. A learning task should be given in the context. Research focusing only on games, art or entertainment is not included.
4. Role-playing or acting should be included in the context. Gamification is also considered, however gamified experiences that do not include any kind of role-playing will not be taken into consideration. Papers related to film production or post-production will also be eliminated.
5. The papers focusing on a developed application will be included. The prototype and implementation should be reported. Conceptual papers and design documents will also be included. Literature reviews will be excluded, but they will be used for snowballing in a later phase.
6. The papers should be published after 2013, because commercially used headsets appeared in the market as of this year.
7. The papers should be either in English or in German.

3 Selection of Studies

The flow diagram of the selection process can be seen in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: The steps followed in the research

- Initial Search
 - In the initial search, 1107 papers were found: ACM(411), Scopus (123), Tandfonline (297), Wiley (276).
- Removing the duplicates
 - After 26 duplicates were removed there were 1081 papers remaining. The next step was screening the papers according to the titles.
- Title-screening
 - At this step, 722 papers were excluded, leaving 359 papers for the abstract screening.
- Abstract screening
 - 4 papers out of 359 papers could not be retrieved.
 - 355 papers were screened according to the abstracts. 326 papers were omitted. 49 out of 326 papers were excluded because they were literature reviews. These literature reviews were set aside for further screening.
 - 29 papers have been selected for snowballing.
 - The abstracts of the 49 literature reviews have been screened, and 4 literature reviews were appropriate to be used in snowballing. Totally we had 33 papers (29 articles and 4 literature reviews) after the screening of the abstracts.

- Snowballing
 - The snowballing technique was used according to the guidelines in [Wo14]. These 33 Papers were used for forward and backward snowballing: 19 Articles were found by snowballing. Totally 52 papers were brought together for full scan.
- Full Paper Screening
 - 4 of the papers could not be reached.
 - 48 papers were subject to full screening. 20 papers were omitted, and 28 Papers were chosen as a result.

4 Data Extraction

The selected papers have been classified according to 6 different categories.

1. **Domain:** The application domain of the research is noted in this category. This is needed to understand in which fields the social VR applications are used.
2. **Type of acting or role-playing:** The main target of this research is understanding the state of the research in terms of immersive learning social VR applications that give role-playing a major role. This states the first critical appraisal of our study. We are trying to understand if the users have the chance to improvise and to act in a character in a dramatical conflict. This is important, because it is a decisive factor for creating a bridge between arts and education in a learning application. Therefore, data extracted in this category is used for defining the research gap.
3. **Role of virtual agents:** This category defines how the virtual agents are used in the application. Moreover, it also includes the type of virtual agent, if it is LLM based, controlled by a human or if it runs merely procedurally in runtime.
4. **Educational task:** This category gives information about the educational context of the application.
5. **Theoretical framework:** It is important to extract the learning theories used in the studies to later summarize and compare the mostly used theoretical frames for immersive learning in social VR.
6. **Evaluation of prototype:** This category includes various variables due to the experiment. Initially it should be checked if the study includes a prototype. Then the experiment design should be understood. Most of the studies include pre-/post-tests in experiment design. From a pedagogical perspective it is important to learn if the experiment evaluates the learning outcome. This states the second critical appraisal of our study. If this is done, another important point is to see if the experiment controls the level of knowledge retention. Long-term evaluation is a way of finding

out if the learning process is successful or not. Moreover, behavioral analysis of the participants should be done accompanying the self-reflection-based evaluations. Therefore, this category checks the following variables:

- a) Does the study involve an implemented prototype?
- b) If there is an implemented prototype, does the evaluation check the long-term learning outcomes?
- c) If there is an implemented prototype, does the evaluation include a behavioral analysis or does it only rely on self-reflection of the participant?

The data extraction table can be seen in [An26]. The colored cells mark the studies that have two properties:

- The study gives the users the ability to act in a character in a dramatical situation in the learning experience.
- The study includes an evaluation for the learning outcome.

References

- [An26] Anonymous: Data Extraction Table - Scoping Review of Acting in Social Virtual Reality for Immersive Learning. Zenodo, 2026. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21103045>
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